

IODINATION. PART II. STUDIES ON THE IODINATION OF DIFFERENT UNSATURATED ORGANIC COMPOUNDS IN THE DARK IN DIFFERENT NON-POLAR SOLVENTS.

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Investigations on the velocity of addition of iodine to β -amylene and d -pinene in the dark in presence of non-polar solvents have shown that the reaction is termolecular with respect to iodine but unimolecular with respect to the acceptor, *i.e.*, it is quadrimolecular with respect to both. The rate of reaction is not much affected by increase of temperature or by increase in the reaction surface, but it appears to depend to a great extent upon the nature of the solvent.

In this part the results of investigations on the velocity of addition of iodine to β -amylene and d -pinene in the dark in non-polar solvents, *e.g.*, carbon tetrachloride, benzene and carbon disulphide have been described.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The reagents are purified exactly in the same way as has been described in Part I of this series (this Journal, 1941, 18, 171). Fresh solutions were prepared after every 2 days with freshly distilled β -amylene and d -pinene to avoid any formation of peroxide which vitiates the kinetic measurements.

Determination of the Velocity of Reaction.

The reaction cell ($4 \times 4 \times 1$ c.c.) made of plane glass plates fused into one another with a stopper at the top was placed inside a double jacketted metal box wholly covered by means of black cloth so that no light could pass inside the box. The temperature was kept constant by passing, with the help of a circulating pump, water from a thermostat through the annular space of the box.

The velocity of reaction was determined by pipetting out 0.66 c.c. of the reaction mixture by means of a micropipette and titrating iodometrically with 0.01*N*-thiosulphate solution by means of a microburette.

The reaction was studied at different temperatures. For low temperatures an ice-bath was used.

To see the effect of surface on the velocity of reaction, experiments were carried out in presence of quartz sands and glass beads. For this, these were carefully cleaned by washing successively with chromic acid, dilute NaOH, dilute HCl, water and finally by steaming. The experiments were carried out in the reaction cell packed with different amounts of quartz sands or beads.

To see the effect of hydriodic acid on the rate of reaction, saturated solutions of HI in benzene, carbon tetrachloride and carbon disulphide were prepared and used in the experiments. It is to be pointed out that HI has practically very little effect on the reaction rate.

The experimental results on the iodination of β -anylene and *d*-pinene are recorded in Tables I to VIII.

The velocity of reaction was found to be proportional to the concentration of the acceptor and to the cube of the iodine concentration, *i.e.*, the active molecule is probably I_3 . Gróh and Szelestey (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, 162, 333) and Gróh and Takacs (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, 149, 195) have shown that in non-polar solvents I_3 molecules are in equilibrium with I_2 molecules according as

so that

$$[I_6] = C[I_2]^3.$$

The reaction between iodine and the acceptor may be represented in the following way:—

so that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx}{dt} &= k''[I_6][A] - k'[AI_2][I_2]^2 \\ &= k[I_2]^3[A] - k'[AI_2][I_2]^2. \end{aligned}$$

Algebraically the velocity of reaction can be represented as

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k(a-x)^3(b-x) - k'x(a-x)^2 \quad \dots (i)$$

where a and b are the initial concentrations of iodine and the acceptor respectively in gram mols per litre and x is the concentration of the iodo product in gram mols per litre at any time t (min).

At equilibrium,

$$k(a-x_1)^2(b-x_1) = k'(a-x_1)^2x_1$$

where x_1 is the concentration of the iodo product when equilibrium is established.

$$\text{Therefore, } K_e = \frac{k}{k'} = \frac{(a-x_1)^2 \cdot x_1}{(a-x_1)^2(b-x_1)} = \frac{x_1}{(a-x_1)(b-x_1)} \quad \dots \text{ (ii)}$$

where K_e is the equilibrium constant.

From (i) we have

$$\frac{dx}{(a-x)^2[k(a-x)(b-x) - k'x]} = dt$$

or

$$\frac{dx}{(a-x)^2(\xi_1-x)(\xi_2-x)} = kdt \quad \dots \text{ (iii)}$$

where ξ_1 and ξ_2 are the roots of the equation

$$\lambda^2 - \frac{kb + ka + k'}{k} \lambda + ab = 0. \quad \dots \text{ (iv)}$$

From (iv) on solving we get $\xi_1 = \frac{ab}{x_1}$ and $\xi_2 = x_1$, where x_1 is the concentration of the reaction product at equilibrium. Now, in order to integrate (iii) we must resolve the fraction

$$\frac{1}{(a-x)^2(\xi_1-x)(\xi_2-x)}$$

into partial fractions thus

$$\frac{1}{(a-x)^2(\xi_2-x)(\xi_1-x)} = \frac{A}{(a-x)^2} + \frac{A_1}{(a-x)} + \frac{B}{(\xi_1-x)} + \frac{C}{(\xi_2-x)}$$

where A , A_1 , B , and C are constants.

From this identity on reduction to a common denominator, we get on equating coefficients of like powers in the two numerators the values of these constants as

$$A = \frac{1}{(\xi_1 - a)(\xi_2 - a)} ;$$

$$A_1 = \frac{2a - (\xi_1 + \xi_2)}{(\xi_1 - a)^2(\xi_2 - a)^2} ;$$

$$B = \frac{1}{(a - \xi_1)^2(\xi_2 - \xi_1)} ;$$

and

$$C = \frac{1}{(a - \xi_2)^2(\xi_1 - \xi_2)}$$

Hence

$$\int \frac{dx}{(a-x)^2(\xi_1-x)(\xi_2-x)} = \int k dt$$

$$\text{or } A \int \frac{dx}{(a-x)^2} + A_1 \int \frac{dx}{(a-x)} + B \int \frac{dx}{(\xi_1-x)} + C \int \frac{dx}{(\xi_2-x)} = \int k dt$$

$$\text{or } \frac{A}{(a-x)} - A_1 \ln(a-x) - B \ln(\xi_1-x) - C \ln(\xi_2-x) = kt + \text{constant.}$$

In the initial stages when $t=0$ and $x=0$

$$\frac{A}{a} - A_1 \ln a - B \ln \xi_1 - C \ln \xi_2 = \text{constant.}$$

Therefore

$$\frac{A.x}{2.303(a-x).a} + A_1 \log \frac{a}{a-x} + B \log \frac{\xi_1}{\xi_1-x} + C \log \frac{\xi_2}{\xi_2-x} = \frac{kt}{2.303}$$

i.e., $k =$

$$\frac{2.303}{t} \left[\frac{A.x}{2.303(a-x).a} + A_1 \log \frac{a}{a-x} + B \log \frac{\xi_1}{\xi_1-x} + C \log \frac{\xi_2}{\xi_2-x} \right] \dots (v)$$

The velocity constants have been calculated from the relation (v) which has been found to hold good very satisfactorily.

R E S U L T S.

A few typical experiments are recorded below.

TABLE I.

Acceptor = β -amylene. Solvent = CCl_4 . Temp. (θ) = 30° .

EXPT. 1.			EXPT. 2.		
$a = 0.0665M$; $b = 0.1M$; $K_r = 5.7$; $x_1 = 0.0208M$.			$a = 0.08135M$; $b = 0.1M$; $K_r = 5.7$; $x_1 = 0.02453M$.		
<i>t.</i>	<i>a-x.</i>	<i>k.</i>	<i>t.</i>	<i>a-x.</i>	<i>k.</i>
0	0.0665		0	0.08135	
10	0.0635	11.6	7	0.0775	11.7
25	0.0603	11.2	12	0.0753	11.8
45	0.0571	11.4	25	0.0717	11.5
mean 11.4			mean 11.7		

EXPT. 3.			EXPT. 4.		
$a = 0.04005M$; $b = 0.2M$; $K_r = 5.7$; $x_1 = 0.02105M$.			$a = 0.083M$; $b = 0.2M$; $K_r = 5.7$; $x_1 = 0.03966M$.		
<i>t.</i>	<i>a-x.</i>	<i>k.</i>	<i>t.</i>	<i>a-x.</i>	<i>k.</i>
0	0.04005		0	0.083	
15	0.03812	11.1	10	0.073	11.7
40	0.03578	10.5	25	0.06586	10.4
70	0.03375	10.1	45	0.0595	10.5
mean 10.6			mean 10.9		

Similar calculations were made in all the experiments and the results are summarised in Tables II to VIII.

Effect of varying the Concentrations of Reactants.

TABLE II.

Temp. = 30° . Acceptor = β -amylene.

Solvent: CCl_4 .			Solvent: C_6H_6 .			Solvent: CS_2 .		
<i>a.</i>	<i>b.</i>	<i>k.</i>	<i>a.</i>	<i>b.</i>	<i>k.</i>	<i>a.</i>	<i>b.</i>	<i>k.</i>
0.083M	0.2M	10.9	0.1M	0.198M	15.1	0.0776M	0.178M	3.8
0.0536	"	11.9	0.075	"	15.1	0.066	"	3.7
0.04005	"	10.6	0.05	"	15.0	0.0543	"	3.8
0.0268	"	10.3	0.025	"	15.4	0.039	"	4.1
0.08135	0.1	11.7	0.075	0.099	15.3	0.0543	0.355	4.0
0.0665	"	11.4	0.05	"	15.1	"	0.267	3.8
0.0334	"	11.6	0.025	"	15.2	"	0.089	3.8
0.0542	0.3	11.2	0.05	0.297	15.6			
"	0.2	11.3	"	0.149	16.0			
"	0.1	11.8						
"	0.05	11.7						

TABLE III.

Solvent = CCl_4 . Temp. = 29° . Acceptor = Pinene.

a.	b.	$k \times 10^{-1}$.	a.	b.	$k \times 10^{-1}$
0'01475M	0'04M	18'6	0'0418	0'08	18'6
0'0211	"	18'2	0'0627	"	19'5
0'0295	"	19'3	0'0211	0'02	19'3
0'0209	0'08	17'4	"	0'03	18'6
			"	0'06	18'7

TABLE IV_FTemp. = 21° . Acceptor = Pinene.

Solvent: C_6H_6 .			Solvent: CS_2 .		
a.	b.	$k \times 10^{-1}$.	a.	b.	$k \times 10^{-1}$
0'02078M	0'083M	89'9	0'02M	0'08M	10'2
0'03905	"	92'1	0'04	"	10'3
0'062	"	90'4	0'06	"	10'5
0'02078	0'02	92'4	0'02	0'02	10'0
"	0'04	92'5	"	0'03	10'1
"	0'06	90'9	"	0'04	10'5
			"	0'06	10'8

Effect of Temperature.

TABLE V.

Acceptor = β -amylene.

Solvent: CCl_4 .			Solvent: C_6H_6 .			Solvent: CS_2 .		
θ .	b.	k.	θ .	b.	k.	θ .	a.	k.
$a = 0'0542M$.			$a = 0'075M$.			$b = 0'1785M$.		
30'0	0'2M	11'3	30'0	0'198M	15'1	30'0	0'078M	3'8
8'0	"	9'9	9'0	"	15'1	6'0	"	3'6
30'0	0'1	11'8	30'0	0'099	15'3	30'0	0'066	3'7
8'0	"	10'5	9'0	"	15'4	6'0	"	3'7

TABLE VI.

Acceptor = Pinene.

Solvent: CCl_4 .			Solvent: C_6H_6 .			Solvent: CS_2 .		
θ .	a.	$k \times 10^{-1}$.	θ .	b.	$k \times 10^{-1}$.	θ .	a.	$k \times 10^{-1}$.
	b = 0.08M.			a = 0.02078M.			b = 0.08M.	
29°0	0.0209M	17.4	21°0	0.08M	89.9	21°0	0.02M	10.2
0°0	"	17.4	8°0	"	93.4	8°0	"	10.6
29°0	0.0418	18.6	21°0	0.04	92.5	21°0	0.04	10.3
0°0	"	19.8	8°0	"	92.5	8°0	"	11.2

Effect of Increasing the Surface.

TABLE VII.

Acceptor = β -anulene.

Solvent.	θ .	Quartz sand.	a.	b.	k.
CCl_4	30°	Nil.	0.0542M	0.3M	11.2
	"	6 g.	"	"	13.3
	"	9	"	"	13.4
C_6H_6	"	Nil	0.05	0.297	15.6
	"	9	"	"	11.8
CS_2	"	Nil	"	0.2	3.8
	"	9	"	"	4.1

TABLE VIII.

Acceptor = Pinene.

Solvent.	θ .	Nature of surface.	a.	b.	$k \times 10^{-1}$.
C_6H_6	21°	Without bead or sand	0.02078M	0.08M	89.9
"	"	With glass bead (9 g.)	"	"	80.2
"	"	With quartz sand (9 g.)	"	"	77.3

The Tables VII and VIII show that the reaction velocity is not much affected by the increase in surface. It is to be mentioned here that the quartz sands taken were so large in amount that there was no free liquid of the reaction mixture over the surface of sand and the entire liquid was in a thin film over the surface of the sand particles.

DISCUSSION.

The reaction has the following characteristics :—

1. The reaction is termolecular with respect to iodine and unimolecular with respect to the acceptor, *i.e.* it is quadrimolecular with respect to both.
2. The reaction rate is much less affected by increase or decrease in temperature. According to the Von Halban-Dhar rule polymolecular reactions have, as a rule, smaller temperature coefficients than unimolecular ones. This rule seems applicable to the cases investigated in this paper.
3. The reaction rate is much less affected by increase in reaction surface which indicates that the reaction is homogeneous.
4. The rate of the reaction depends to a great extent on the nature of solvent. It is greatest in C_6H_6 and least in CS_2 .

The following mechanism will explain the observed facts.

We can assume according to the observations made by Gröh *et al* (*loc. cit.*) that in non-polar solvents like CCl_4 , C_6H_6 and CS_2 iodine molecules (I_2) exist in equilibrium with hexa-atomic iodine molecules (I_6) in the following way :—

Now these I_6 molecules are responsible for the thermal iodination.

The reaction may be expressed by

so that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx}{dt} &= k''[I_6][A] - k'[AI_2][I_2]^2 \\ &= k[I_2]^3[A] - k'[AI_2][I_2]^2 \\ &= k(a-x)^3(b-x) - k'.x.(a-x)^2 \end{aligned} \quad \dots (I)$$

where a and b are the initial concentrations of iodine and the acceptor respectively and x , the concentration of the iodo product in time t minute.

The equation (I) has been found to be very satisfactory.

As regards the influence of solvents used in this investigation, in benzene the velocity is considerably greater than for the other non-polar solvents. This difference is difficult to explain as all the three non-polar solvents have low dielectric constants.